

TECHNICAL AND VOCATIONAL EDUCATION AND POVERTY REDUCTION: THE CASE OF NIGERIA.

Ilori David Babafemi

Department of Management Sciences,

College of Social and Management Sciences, Wesley University of Science and Technology, Ondo.

KEYWORDS: Technical and Vocational Education, skill acquisition, Poverty, Informal sector, Funding, and Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

Despite the contributions of technical education to national development, the leaders of Nigeria have not given this sector the attention it deserves. In spite of the strong emphasis on skills development for poverty reduction found in national policies, programmes and projections, it is not clear how the Government of Nigeria plans to realise its ambitions in this direction. The government at several fora had come up with high sounding proposals and development plans aimed at stemming the scourge of poverty and unemployment in Nigeria like the case of national policy geared towards technical education, but all efforts, as it were, failed to yield the desired result. This is because the relationship between skills development and poverty alleviation is neither simple nor automatic. It is against this background that this paper seeks to evaluate governments' efforts and commitments to technical and vocational education in Nigeria and the possible way forward. The paper makes a campaign for a prodigious investment in skill acquisition if Nigeria will ever achieve its vision 2020 goal; realize economic growth and development evidenced with employment opportunities and an increasing life expectancy. A case is also made for the informal sector, realising that the productive capacity of this economic unit is sub-optimal as a result of lack of both pre and post training opportunities.

INTRODUCTION

The need to promote technical and vocational education and to imbue graduates with the mindset of enterprise and innovativeness is gathering momentum among nations of the world. There is a fresh awareness among policy makers in many African countries and the international donor community of the critical role that technical and vocational education and training (TVET) can play in national development. According to Bhuwanea (2006), in recent years, concerns have been raised by most African countries about the move towards making TVET complementary to post-basic education. Prior to the present dispensation, Nigerians have historically considered technical and vocational education and training (TVTE) as an education programme meant for low level, low brilliant and less privileged or second class citizens (Okoro, 1993, and Eze and Okorafor, 2012). Iheonunekwu, Nwamuo and Eze (2011) noted that from all ramifications and to a number of reasons, Vocational Education is for people who are not intelligent enough to do academic work. However, in the recent time, the campaign for technical education and skill acquisition is gathering momentum in the country.

Vocational and Technical Education (VTE) systems play a crucial role in the social and economic development of a nation. Owing to their dynamic nature, they are continuously subject to the forces driving change in the schools, industry and society. The major educational reforms according to Daniel (2001) have, however, been on vocationalisation. It is in line with this, that different countries have come up with different framework towards repositioning their vocational and technical programmes. Technical education facilitates the acquisition of practical and applied skills as well as basic scientific knowledge, it is therefore a planned program of courses and learning experiences that begins with exploration of career options, supports basic academic and life skills, and enables achievement of high academic standards, leadership, preparation for industry-defined work, and advanced and continuing education (CTE, 2009). Cinterfor/ILO (2006) stated that VTE can be a tool to counteract at least in part, the harmful effect of unemployment by promoting greater job turnover and guarding against the risks of obsolescence.

8TH – 9TH, OCTOBER, 2013

However, in view of the benefits accruing to Technical and Vocational education (TEV) and the global challenge of the time, Nigeria therefore has joined her world counterparts in formulating policies geared towards ensuring a national system of vocational education. A system that ensures that, young people see vocational education as challenging and worthwhile. Although, in the recent time, the nations' emphasis on technical education appears to be gathering momentum, yet it is not clear how the government of Nigeria plans to realise its ambitions in this direction realising the fact that under-funding has been the bane of vocational and technical education in Nigeria. According to Fafunwa (2010), Nigeria has money but lacks the ability to use it judiciously. Dike (2009) stressed that vocational education holds the key for the solution of Nigeria's developmental problems, yet it is the worst applied instrument for national development. Considering Vocational and Technical Education as the key for national development (Dike, 2009), it is imperative for this sector to be adequately funded to make it result- driven.

Unfortunately, Nigeria does not seem to give technical and vocational education the attention they deserve and this appears to be one of the reasons for rising unemployment and poverty in the society. It is against this background that this paper seeks to evaluate government efforts and commitment to funding technical education in Nigeria with the aim of making recommendations for the way forward. A case is also made for the informal sector, for a scheme to formalize what may be called the training side of the informal sector by way of partnership with the formal sector.

Conceptual Issues

The concept of technical and vocational education varies from country to country thus, are interchangeably used as vocational education and training (VET), technical and vocational education (TVE), technical and vocational education and training (TVET), vocational technical education (VTE), or vocational and technical education and training (VOTEC). They all mean the same thing.

Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004) opined that vocational technical education is an aspect of the educational process involving, in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences and the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge relative to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life. Manfred and Jennifer (2004) advocated that vocational technical education comprises all more or less organized or structured activities that aim at providing people with the knowledge, skills and competencies necessary to perform a job or a set of jobs whether or not they lead to a formal qualification. These definitions show that the relationship between VTE and employments is undeniable. Thus, any education that is geared towards teaching technical skills and attitudes suitable to such skills can be regarded as technical education.

Others have noted that skills development appears to be a much broader concept than technical and vocational education and training (TVET), (Working Group for International

Cooperation in Skills Development, 2002: 11). With these qualifications in mind, therefore, skills development is not equated with formal technical, vocational and agricultural education and training alone, but is used more generally to refer also to the productive capacities acquired through all levels of education and training, occurring in formal, non-formal and on-the-job settings.

Poverty affects many aspects of human conditions; hence there has been no universal concern on the definition. Poverty according to Ozoike (2002) is a condition below that of ease and comfortable living in any area of life; physically, mentally, socially and financially. The concept of poverty includes material deprivation, (e.g food, shelter) and access to services (e.g health, education). It tends to encompass a range of non- material conditions such as a lack of rights, insecurity, powerlessness and indignity (Vandenberg, 2006).

Skill development and poverty reduction

There is still a strong sense that the capacities acquired through skills training or skills development are linked to particular livelihoods, occupations and work – whether in industry, commerce, agriculture or micro-enterprise. Yinka (2013) quipped that skill training is critical for sustainable industrialisation and

VENUE: FRANCIS IDIBIYE HALL, FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY, AKURE, ONDO STATE, NIGERIA

8TH – 9TH, OCTOBER, 2013

poverty reduction in terms of creating a critical mass of technically and entrepreneurially qualified people. United Nations emphasized human development, measured by life expectancy, adult literacy, access to all three levels of education, as well as people's average income which is a necessary condition of their freedom of choice. The UNESCO International Project on Technical and Vocational Education (UNEVOC) (2006), emphasized that since education is considered the key to effective development strategies, technical and vocational education and training (TVET) must be the master key that can alleviate poverty, promote peace, conserve the environment, improve the quality of life for all and help achieve sustainable development. The above, therefore, lend credence to the fact TVET has the potential to curb high rates of unemployment in Nigeria especially among youths and women.

TVE Funding in Nigeria – An Evaluation

It is difficult to deny government's role in the funding of Vocational and Technical Education especially after independence. The Federal Government therefore had substantially improved expenditure in this area in the third and fourth National Development Plan period in addition to establishing such agencies as the ITF and the erstwhile Petroleum Trust Fund (PTF) to assist in the development of technological education in the country. Offiong, A. Anthony (2013). However available statistics show that we are not there yet.

While the allocation to education in Nigeria's 2013 budget proposal presented to the joint session of the National Assembly on Wednesday, October 10, 2012 by President Goodluck Jonathan tops those of other sectors, the amount is still far below the standard set by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO). The proposed allocation of N426.53 billion to the sector takes only 8.67 percent of the proposed total budget of N4.92 trillion, whereas the UNESCO recommended for the allocation of 26 percent of the total sector to the sector which is very vital to national development. Ifeoma (2004). An insignificant proportion of Nigeria's financial resources are spent on education. Education budgets as percentages of total national budgets were 8.43% in 2012 and 8.67% in 2013. These fell below those of other developing countries. Ghana, South Africa, Cote d'Ivoire, Kenya and Morocco had 31%, 25.8%, 30%, 23% and 17.7% respectively of their annual budget for education (Abayomi 2012). The United Nations recommends that 26 per cent of the total expenditure be devoted to education.

If the above is the situation for education in Nigeria, then, under-funding is still the bane of Vocational and Technical Education in Nigeria as could be seen in the inadequacy of infrastructure, human resources and equipment in many institutions at the secondary to tertiary levels.

The need for adequate funding of VTE

Poverty could be reduced when TVET are well funded which will invariably develop the nation. The apparent neglect of technical education is socially and economically injurious because it is robbing the nation the contributions the graduates would make on national development. According to Manfred and Jennifer (2004), industrialized countries are transforming themselves into knowledge society by investing more on human resources. This implies that productivity and competitiveness of Nigeria in the economic world order is dependent on a well-educated, skilled and adaptable workforce. The importance of proper funding of Vocational and Technical Education has been acknowledged by many educationists like Adesina (1977), Ukeje (1977), Akpan (2010). They all agreed that since the programme is capital intensive, proper implementation and actualization of its set goals will not be achieved without adequate funding.

At present, most of our institutions running TVET courses do not have reliable learning workshops as they are equipped with conventional machines which are not in line with the trend of development and the ones they will be exposed to in the standing manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Also, graduates lack the requisite skills today as a result of inadequate funding of TVET because instructors, technicians and craftsmen that possess the dexterity of industrial technical acts are not available in the schools due to poor remuneration occasioned by poor funding of the education sector. There is, therefore, the need for effective funding of technical education in the country otherwise Nigeria will continue to wear the toga of poverty and remain a laggard in preparing its labour force for the 21st century economy.

Informal sector and the economy

8TH – 9TH, OCTOBER, 2013

The informal sector refers to the very large micro and small enterprise economy in urban and rural areas, outside the formal sector. Enterprises are often unregistered and untaxed. It is not an exaggeration to state that the large gaps left by the formal training and employment systems are filled by informal arrangements. In addition to employment in the informal sector, formal enterprises also rely heavily on informal, on-the-job training.

Informal skill acquisition is also associated with a sense of economic independence and security of income. In this context, it is evident that any effective strategy for poverty reduction through skills development cannot afford to neglect the informal sector. The informal sector and the local apprenticeship system present a development paradox: they are crucially important to employment generation and to the transfer of skills across generations. Yet, government response has generally been more negative than positive.

Training in the Informal or Unorganized Sector

The supply of training outside the formal economy is widely acknowledged to be the main pathway for skills acquisition and utilization in many countries. And what has been said above about the enabling economic environment applies directly to this sector. Policy makers are now much more aware of the scale of such training, as compared to formal TVE or TVET, and they are attracted by the sheer size of the youth population that is involved in acquiring skills in this part of the private sector. There is the need to co-opt the informal sector into skill acquisition in the tertiary institutions realising the fact that lack of access to basic education grossly affects their contribution to the economy. The irony is this. In some cases, our tertiary institutions do take their students who offer entrepreneurial courses to technicians, mechanics, fashion designers, vulcanisers, computer ‘engineers’ etc in the informal sector for practical training and skill acquisition but unfortunately, some of these supposed instructors are not well educated thus, giving rise to communication problem and inefficient delivery. Schemes to formalize what may be called the training side of the informal sector abound, including of the informal apprenticeship system. These can involve upgrading masters, organizing access to theory related to the practical skills being acquired, promoting certification of informally acquired skills, even the proposed funding of the apprentices’ first year. (Johanson, 2009: 53)

Funding of Technical and Vocational Education in Nigeria – The Way Forward

Globally, the drive to mobilize finance for TVET is much weaker than efforts to raise resources for academic schooling or higher education. The problem of financing vocational-technical education appears intractable. And, according to Onwueme (1995), “if vocational technical education is considered crucial for our technological needs, then a reappraisal of national priorities is required so as to give vocational technical education the place it deserves.” However, this demands conscious efforts from all stakeholders rather than mere rhetoric. Rather than solely relying on the government for funding and capacity building through skills acquisition both in the formal and informal windows, an attempt will be made to highlight for other possible options.

- 1. Public- private partnership:** Constitutionally, local government authorities are responsible for funding primary education, while states fund secondary education. Tertiary institutions are funded by the proprietors including the federal, state and private owners. However, the resources required to transform Nigeria education sector cannot be provided by government alone. There is therefore, the need to solicit Public-Private Partnership (PPP) because Vocational and Technical Education is capital intensive which requires more workshops, equipment and other facilities which the state may not be able to fund alone. Any new thinking and focus for public-private model will enhance the contributions of private initiatives, investors and technocrats to the effectiveness of TVE in Nigeria towards revamping the economy.
- 2. Partnership with International Donors:** In today’s increasingly integrated world, harnessing opportunities from well-coordinated activities of the international donors such as International Development Partners (IDPs) are critical to strategic investment in TVE. As NGOs, their aim is to provide affordable health care, clean and reliable water, education, agriculture among others to low-income countries. The world has changed fundamentally since the adoption of the Millennium Declaration. It is faced with new challenges and opportunities, many of which require collective action. Most importantly, it will have to be based on a strong commitment to engage in collective actions with a clear distribution of

8TH – 9TH, OCTOBER, 2013

tasks between developed and developing countries. IDPs work with local civil societies, organisations and government authorities in developing countries. Therefore, partnering with international donors for greater TVE funding is another avenue that could be explored to generate fund for TVE in Nigeria. The above will serve as a way of supplementing the assistance which the nation's education sector has been enjoying from International Organisations such as World Bank, UNESCO among others.

3. Tax rebates and credit schemes: In most regions other than Latin America, Tax Rebates or Tax Credit system is more frequently used. In Tax Rebates, a portion of the tax is returned to the firm as subsidy for training. In Singapore and Tunisia, the rebate is on the basis of costs incurred. In Nigeria, this can be in the form of grants to set up training systems. This will help enterprises who are into training and skill development on employees overcome teething problem arising from funding.

4. Vocational training funds: In many countries where employers are active participants in VET, a training fund for financing vocational training has been set up. Tax contributions from the employers collected through payroll levies as well as subsidies from the government are transferred to the Training Fund. In Nigeria, this should not be the same as Education Trust Fund but a separate fund that is legally reserved for VET. Management of funds can be handled by the Ministry of Education, the employers association and the workers' unions. This is a useful way securing cooperation as well as formulation of appropriate training policy for both the formal and informal sectors.

5. Internally Generated Revenue Opportunities: Training and vocational Institutes can generate income from the sale of services to public and private enterprises or individuals. Even in the area of technical education, students can be made to engage in product manufacturing for their assessment under the guidance and supervision of their teachers. By this approach, technical education institutions in Nigeria are likely to be revenue yielding to the favour of their continued and productive existence. A management committee could then be set up to liquidate these products to the public in a widely publicized open day in order to generate revenue for the school. Also, school halls could be rented out for public functions like, weddings, church activities, conduct and marking of external examinations and other social meetings. And again, some TVETs offer non-training services such as consultancies. Fees from this could be paid to the government or the training institution. In the informal sector, the apprentice or the recipient of such services pays their master or the Training Institute.

6. Paid educational leave: Another pattern of financing vocational and industrial education in some countries is the provision of paid educational leave. Employers continue to pay wages to employees while they receive part time or full time vocational education. Therefore paid educational leave also becomes another way of distributing costs between the employers, workers and tax payers (Woodhall, 1987). The interesting thing about this is that the failure of our technical schools and tertiary institutions to produce technically and entrepreneurially qualified people arising from funding problem can be compensated for through on-the-job training opportunities.

7. Corporate Social Responsibility: In addition to corporation tax, business organisations do take greater roles in the society to achieve several economic, education and social objectives as part of their corporate social responsibilities. They do this as a way of giving back to the public and to project their goodwill and therefore, training and technical institutions can woo corporate bodies to harness such financial assistance. The fund can go through the government or directly to technical institutions.

CONCLUSION

Vocational education has always been given the shorter end of the stick when it comes to statutory allocation of finances by the government. This notwithstanding, the resources required to transform TVET cannot be provided by government alone if Nigeria will ever achieve economic growth and development evidenced with employment opportunities and increasing life expectancy. There is therefore, the need to solicit for other sources of funding because of the capital intensive nature of Vocational and Technical Education. Diversifying financing will create greater opportunities and improve the quality of training. Governments have to realise that funding from public revenue is not the only way to finance investment in vocational education and training. There should be a determination to involve employers, international donor agencies, individuals and the corporate body. Also, there is the need to co-opt the informal sector into skill acquisition in the tertiary institutions, realising that lack of access to basic education grossly affects their contribution to the economy. In this context, it is evident that any effective strategy for poverty reduction through skills acquisition and development cannot afford to neglect the informal sector otherwise

the nation's vision 2020 remains elusive and the resultant effect will sink the nation in the mud of poverty and technological backwardness.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In a bid to improve on the funding status of Vocational and Technical Education in Nigeria the paper recommends the following:

1. All stakeholders in education, industry and Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) should jointly fund and train/develop the students for the acquisition of employable skills to meet the demand of industry and the sophisticated technology in this technological era.
2. There is the need for the government to streamline bureaucratic process and create enabling environment for greater private sector participation in funding of TVE.
3. Institutions involved in Vocational and Technical Education should intensify more effort to realize internally generated revenue through consultancy services, rental services of school hall and showcasing their products for public sale.
4. When funds are released for capital and non-capital projects, monitoring and impact assessment procedures must necessarily be carried out to avoid such funds going down the drain.
5. Support should be sought from Development Partners and other International donors e.g. World Bank, UNESCO.
6. There is the need to separate TVE fund from the general education in state allocations.
7. Financial support should also be sought from corporate organisations under their corporate social responsibility policy.
8. Governments at all level must be pressured to devote the recommended 26% of their budgets to education by UNESCO. Out of this, we should demand that at least about 50% should be allocated to Technical Vocational Education.
9. In the case of the informal sector, there should be schemes to formalize what may be called the training side of the informal sector. These can involve organizing access to theory related to the practical skills being acquired, promoting certification of informally acquired skills through diploma and certificate courses in the tertiary institutions as a way integrating both the formal and non- formal TVET.
10. Also, it is important that the two TVET systems that is, formal and non-formal are piloted by a single national coordinating body in order to facilitate articulation between the two systems and enhance coherence and better management of the entire TVET system.

REFERENCES

- Abayomi, A. (2012). Education budget and its implications (Analysis). Retrieved from <http://www.vanguardngr.com/>.
- Adesina, S. (1977). *Planning and education development in Nigeria: Academy at development in Nigeria*. Lagos: Academy Press Ltd.
- Akpan, G. A. (2010). Approaches for involving communities in providing financial resources for vocational education. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Review*, 1(1), 154 – 159.
- Bhuwanee, T. (2006). Reforming technical and vocational education in Sub-Saharan Africa: *Case studies of Ghana - Mauritius - Tanzania and Zimbabwe*. Dakar, Senegal
- Cinterfor/ILO (2006). Vocational training and employment promotion- Cinterfor: *Inter American Research and Documentation Centre in Vocational Training*.
- (CTE)(2009): Washington-Office of Superintendent of Public Instruction: <http://www.k12.wa.us/CareerTechEd/>
- Daniel, N.S. (2001). African education in the twenty-first century: The challenge for change. *Journal of International Cooperation in Education*, 14 (1), 21 38.

Dike, V. E. (2009). Technical and vocational education: Key to Nigeria's development. Retrieved from <http://www.triuphnewspapers.com/tech3032009.html>

Eze, T. I. & Okorafor, O A. (2012). Trends in technical, vocational education and training for improving the Nigerian workforce. *Ebonyi Vocational and Technology Education Journal*. 1(1), 107-115.

Fafunwa, H. B. (2010). Classes are bid for failure before examination itself. *The Nigerian Education Times*, 30:20-21.

Federal Republic of Nigeria (2004). *National policy in education* (4th ed.) Lagos. NERDC Press.

Iheonunekwu, S. Nwanmo, C.N. & Eze, Rock, O. (2011). Reappraising the employ ability skills of technical and vocational education student in Nigeria. *Journal of Qualitative Education, Nigeria*. 7 (1) 12-22.

Johanson, R., (2009). Good practice in technical and vocational education and training. *Asian Development Bank*, Manila. (2).

Manfred, T and Jennifer, W. (2004). *Vocational education and training: Key to the future*. Greece: Colibri Ltd.

Offiong, A. (2013). Funding of vocational and technical education in Nigeria in times of global economic recession. *An International Journal of Arts and Humanities*. Bahir Dar, Ethiopia Vol. 2 (2), S/No 6, May, 2013: 149-158

Okoro, O. M. (1993). *Principles and methods in vocational and technical education*. Nsukka University. Trust Publication.

Onwueme, M.S. 1995. *Issues and problems of technical education: Trends in vocational education in Nigeria*. Lagos, Nigeria: NERC Press.

Ozoike, B.U. (2002). *Victory over poverty*. Enugu, Nigeria. Cheston Publications Ltd.

UNEVOC (2006). An international experts' meeting organised by the UNESCO-UNEVOC International centre for technical and vocational education and training (TVET). Bonn, Germany.

Vandenberg, P. (2006): Poverty reduction through enterprises emerging consensus: Unresolved issues and ILO activities, *SEED Working Paper*, No. 75.

Woodhall, M. (1987). *Financing vocational and industrial education: Economics of education research and studies*, edited by Psacharopoulos, G. Pergamon Press, Oxford.